

Performance of Francis Turbine and Hydro Electric Governing

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ABSTRACT

The Main requirement for hydro-electric power plant is the availability of water in huge quantity at sufficient head and this requirement can be met by constructing a dam across a river. A storage reservoir is formed by constructing a dam across Krishna River. Near the bottom of the dam, there is a water intake. Trash Racks of 38meters long are provided at the water intake to prevent the ingress of floating and other materials to the turbine. A Power tunnel of 720m long and diameter of 50 feet is taken off from the reservoir to the valve house at the start of Penstock. From the reservoir the water is carried to valve house through power tunnel and from valve house to the water Turbine through pipes of large diameter 6.10m made of steel or reinforced concrete, called the Penstock. The shaft from the turbine goes up into the 3-phase Alternator of capacity 122000KVA, which produces the power. The water after having done its useful work in the turbine is discharged to the tail race which may lead it to the river. The Srisailem Power plant has the capacity of 7×110 MW. To control the water flow so the other alternative governor is Electro Hydraulic Governor -100. Electro Hydraulic Governor -100 can operate very efficiently.

Keyword: Penstock, Shaft, Turbine, Governor, Dam.

INTRODUCTION

The River Krishna is one of the major river systems in peninsular India and its basin has been and continues to be the cradle of civilization since ancient. Srisailem and Nagarjuna Sagar dams constructed one below the other on this river form two of the largest manmade lakes with combined gross storage of over 700 TMC ft. (20,000 million cubic meters). Such a system of two large reservoirs in cascade (one below the other) is unique. This affords development of Hydel Power in the conventional as well as pumped storage mode.

Fig.1 Hydro electric dam

Fig 2: Schematic view of hydroelectric dam

Type of turbine	Francis
Diameter of runner	3600 mm
Speed of rotation	187.5 rpm
Runaway speed	375 rpm
Maximum (H Max)	104.85 m
Design (HD)	91.44 m
Minimum (H min)	71.32 m
Rated output of turbine (at design head)	112200 kw
Maximum output of turbine (at head 99 m and above)	123500 kw
Discharge through the turbine at design head and rated output	137.5 m ³ /sec
Optimum efficiency of the turbine	93%
Speed rise of the set at 100% load throw drop	55%
Maximum pressure rise	35%

Type of governor	Electro-hydraulic
Type of inlet valve	Disc valve diameter 4200 mm
Direction of rotation(when viewed from generator end)	Clockwise
Maximum axial load transferred from on generator thrust bearings from turbine	382 T

Governor

To control the speed of the turbine we need a Governor. First the electronic Governor senses the speed of the turbine and compares it with the reference speed, and the error signal is processed through PID controller and drives the Actuator of the Hydraulic governor. The actuator supplies the control oil to auxiliary servomotor through load limiter. As the auxiliary servomotor is mechanically linked with the pilot valve spool of the Main Distributing Valve (MDV), the displacement of auxiliary servomotor controls the MDV spool lift and there by controls gate servomotor and gate operating and wicket gates. Thus the speed of the turbine will be controlled.

TYPES OF GOVERNORS:

Mechanical governor:

A purely mechanical speed governing system, the speed is mechanically sensed and governed from a rotating output of the prime mover. In addition, the work to control the fuel metering device is derived from this rotational output.

Hydraulic governor:

A hydraulic governor is similar to the mechanical governor in the means of sensing and governing speed; however, the work from the fuel control mechanism is produced by control of a pressurized hydraulic source.

Electronic governor:

An electronic governor is a system in which the prime mover speed is electrically sensed and governed. The output force for the actuator is entirely electro-magnetic. The output force is dependent on an outside source of electrical energy, such as a storage battery.

Electro-hydraulic governor:

An electro-hydraulic governor is a system in which the prime mover speed is electrically sensed. The output force of the electro-hydraulic actuator, however, is hydraulic in nature much the same as the hydraulic governor. An electrical command from the speed governor circuit determines the output position of the actuator.

Electro Hydraulic GOVERNOR

PERFORMANCE OF THE FRANCIS TURBINE: The performance of turbines under unit head facilitates the comparison of turbines of same type. The unit head characteristics are **UNIT POWER (PU):**

It is the power developed by a given turbine, when head is one meter and η_o overall efficiency remains the same. Power, $P=WQH\eta_o/75$

$$P \propto QH$$

$$Q = K\pi DBVf, \text{ for a reaction turbine}$$

$$Q \propto V f \text{ for the same turbine}$$

$$P \propto V f H$$

$$P \propto H^{1/2} H$$

$$P \propto (H)^{3/2}$$

$$P = K1 (H)^{3/2}$$

Where K1 = Constant

By definition of unit power, If H = 1 m, Then

$$P = K1 = Pu$$

$$P = Pu (H)^{3/2}$$

$$Pu = P / (H)^{3/2} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

1. UNIT SPEED (Nu):

It is the speed of the turbine, when working under a head of one meter and as same.

$$U = \pi DN/60$$

$$D \propto U/N$$

$$U \propto H^{1/2}$$

$$D = \sqrt{H/N}$$

$$N \propto \sqrt{H} \quad (\text{as } D = \text{Constant})$$

$$N = K2 \sqrt{H}$$

If H = 1m, N = K2 = Nu (by definition)

$$N = Nu \sqrt{H}$$

$$Nu = N / \sqrt{H} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Thus unit speed of turbine can be obtained by dividing the normal speed (N) by \sqrt{H} .

UNIT DISCHARGE (Qu):

It is the discharge of a given turbine, When working under a head of one meter.

$$Q \propto VF$$

$$Q \propto \sqrt{H}$$

$$Q = K3 \sqrt{H}$$

If H = 1m; Q = K3 = Qu (by definition)

$$Q = Qu \sqrt{H}$$

$$Qu = Q / \sqrt{H} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Specifications:

$$Qu = \pi D (ND) VFU$$

$$Qs = \pi Ds (ND) VFS$$

$$Qu/Qs = (D/Ds)^2$$

$$Pu = W Qu \eta_o$$

$$Ps = W Qs \eta_o$$

$$Pu/Ps = Qu/Qs = (D/Ds)^2$$

$$Ps = 1 KW$$

$$Pu = P / (H)^{3/2}$$

$$Ds = D / \sqrt{Pu}$$

$$Uu = \pi D Nu/60$$

$$Us = \pi Ds Ns/60$$

$$Uu = Us$$

$$\Pi Du Nu/60 = \pi Ds Ns/60$$

$$Ns = Nu (D/Ds) = Nu$$

$$Pu = P / (H)^{3/2}$$

$$Ns = N \sqrt{P / (H)} \square/4 \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$\text{But } Nu = N \sqrt{H}$$

Table-1: Performance of Generating Unit at Constant Head

S. No	HEAD(m)	DISCHARGE (m ³ /sec)	LOAD (MW)	UNIT SPEED	OVERALL EFFICIENCY	UNIT DISCHARGE	UNIT POWER
1	87.6	27.34	10	20.04	31.31	2.92	0.012
2	87.6	39.94	20	20.04	42.87	4.26	0.024
3	87.6	45.25	30	20.04	56.76	4.83	0.036
4	87.6	57.96	40	20.04	59.08	6.19	0.048
5	87.6	70.32	50	20.04	60.87	7.51	0.060
6	87.6	82.76	60	20.04	62.07	8.84	0.073
7	87.6	94.09	70	20.04	63.69	10.05	0.085
8	7.6	105.51	80	20.04	64.91	11.27	0.097
9	87.6	118.16	90	20.04	65.21	12.62	0.1097
10	87.6	123.09	94	20.04	65.38	13.12	0.1146

Table-2: Performance of Generating Unit at Constant Discharge

Sl. No	HEAD (m)	DISCHARGE (m ³ /sec)	LOAD(MW)	UNIT SPEED	OVERALL EFFICIENCY	UNIT DISCHARGE	UNIT POWER
1	80.46	122	81.35	20.90	62.15	13.60	0.1127
2	84.24	122	83.90	20.42	61.22	13.29	0.1085
3	85.31	122	84.88	20.30	61.16	13.20	0.1055
4	85.86	122	83.11	20.23	69.50	13.16	0.1044
5	86.36	122	86.23	20.16	61.38	13.13	0.1074
6	86.56	122	88.14	20.15	62.59	13.11	0.1094
7	87.26	122	87.92	20.07	61.91	13.06	0.1078
8	87.41	122	88.50	20.05K	62.24	13.04	0.1049
9	87.94	122	87.68	19.99	61.29	13.09	0.1070

Table -3: Performance of Generating Unit at Constant Load

S. No	HEAD(m)	DISCHARGE (m ³ /sec)	LOAD(MW)	UNIT SPEED	OVERALL EFFICIENCY	UNIT DISCHARGE	UNIT POWER
1	87.38	149.95	94	20.05	53.80	16.04	0.1150
2	87.47	148.80	94	20.04	54.16	15.82	0.1150
3	87.90	140.09	94	19.99	57.25	14.94	0.1140
4	88.08	139.60	94	19.97	57.33	14.87	0.1137
5	88.33	134.90	94	19.95	59.16	14.35	0.1132
6	88.63	131.06	94	19.91	60.69	13.92	0.1126
7	89.15	127.69	94	19.88	61.93	13.52	0.1116
8	89.24	126.30	94	19.85	62.54	13.37	0.1115
9	89.55	124.07	94	19.81	63.45	13.11	0.1109

RESULT

this process at constant head the efficiency is increases when the discharge also increases.

The graph between the discharge Vs efficiency. Discharge is along with the X-axis and the efficiency is along with Y-axis. In

The graph between the head V_s Discharge. Head is along with the X-axis and the Discharge is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant load the head decreases then automatically the discharge is also decreases.

The graph between the load V_s Efficiency. Load is along with the X-axis and the Efficiency is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant head the load is increases when the efficiency is increases.

The graph between the load V_s head. Load is along with the X-axis and the head is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant discharge the load is increases when the head is increases.

The graph between the head V_s unit power. Head is along with the X-axis and the Unit power is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant load the head is decreases then the unit power is also decreases.

The graph between the head V_s unit discharge .Head is along with the X-axis and the Unit discharge is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant load the head is decreases then the unit discharge is also decreases.

The graph between the unit speed V_s discharge . Unit speed is along with the X-axis and the Discharge is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant load the unit speed is decreases then the discharge is also decreases.

The graph between the unit speed V_s unit discharge .Unit speed is along with the X-axis and the Unit discharge is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant load the unit speed decreases then the unit discharge decreases.

The graph between the unit speed Vs efficiency .Unit speed is along with the X-axis and the Efficiency is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant loads the unit speed increases then the efficiency is also increases.

The graph between the unit speed Vs head .Unit speed is along with the X-axis and the Head is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant loads the unit speed increases then the head increases.

The graph between the unit speed Vs unit power. Unit speed is along with the X-axis and the Unit power is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant loads the unit speed decreases then the unit power is also decreases.

The graph between the discharge Vs load .Discharge is along with the X-axis and the load is along with Y-axis. In this process at constant head the discharge increases then the load increases.

CONCLUSION

The Srisaillam Power plant has the capacity of 7×110 MW. In the hydro electric power plant Francis is used to produce power from the plant. From the dam free flowing water rotates the turbine , it is connected to the generator through a shaft . Water flows irrespective of velocity and pressure , for the controlling the flow according required loads guide vanes are placed and its operated by using a governor (hydro electric governor-100)

To control the water flow so the other alternative governor is Electro Hydraulic Governor -100. It is a combination of hydraulic and electronic governor. It can be operated by automatically or manually.

Feedback mechanism is potentiometer shows the effectiveness of the governor. Especially to avoid the grid failure Electro Hydraulic Governor -100 can operate very efficiently.

We have collected the daily data with that we have drawn the characteristic curves. We conclude the increase in unit speed decreases the power developed by the turbine. The overall efficiency increases with the discharge and remains more or less constant beyond a particular value of discharge. Output is directly proportional to discharge, with the increase in unit speed discharge decreases.

Table : Performance Of Turbine At Variable Conditions

S.no	Performance of turbine at given conditions	Overall efficiency of turbine at variable conditions (H,Q, P)
01	Constant Head	65.38
02	Constant Discharge	69.50
03	Constant Load	63.45

As above given tabular column shows the performance of francis turbine.

NOTE: To control the turbine speed according to the varying loads electro hydraulic governor is used , as to work efficiently electro hydraulic governor-100 is not responding to the SCADA(supervisory control and data acquisition) works , instead of scada based governor we can use microprocessor based governor , to obtain accurate results.

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